

COMPOSITE ACTUATORS MADE OF SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY WIRES AND MULTI-MATRIX FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM)
Belfast, 2023

S. Bruk¹, S. Konze¹, M. Stommel^{1,2} and A. Spickenheuer¹

¹ Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V.

² Technische Universität Dresden, Fakultät Maschinenwesen

1. Introduction and Motivation

Multi-matrix fiber reinforced plastics (MM-FRP)

- Composite structures with locally defined bending zones
- Continuous fiber-reinforcement possible
- 2-step vacuum assisted infiltration process (VAP) for the realization of MM-FRP [1]

- Polyurethane (PU) matrix
- Epoxy (EP) matrix

1. Introduction and Motivation

Tailored fiber placement (TFP)

- Variable-axial fixating of fibrous material via embroidery onto base material [2]
- Suitable for wires, also shape-memory alloy wires

1. Introduction and Motivation

Shape-memory alloy (SMA)

- Smart material with temperature-dependent phase transformation
- Reversible transformation
- Wires as semi finished product with contraction upon heating
- Heating possible via electric current

1. Introduction and Motivation

Actuable composite structures with locally defined bending zones

2. Production of Integral MM-FRP Actuator Structures

Manufacturing process

1. Embroidery of pre-strained SMA-wire onto preform
2. Preparation of preform for matrix application
3. Application of PU-matrix in target area
4. Setup of VAP-mold
5. Curing of PU-Matrix
6. Infiltration and curing of Epoxy resin
7. Tempering of composite
8. De-molding, cutting, finishing

2. Production of Integral MM-FRP Actuator Structures

Manufacturing process

1. Embroidery of pre-strained SMA-wire onto preform
2. Preparation of preform for matrix application
3. Application of PU-matrix in target area
4. Setup of VAP-mold
5. Curing of PU-Matrix
6. Infiltration and curing of Epoxy resin
7. Tempering of composite
8. De-molding, cutting, finishing

Conflicting temperatures:

Transition temperature (austenite-start) of SMA below processing and curing temperature of PU-matrix

→ Loss of actuator capacity possible

Blocking of SMA-wire contraction:

→ Fixation via embroidery (TFP)

→ Fixation by means of tools

2. Production of Integral MM-FRP Actuator Structures

Consolidation tool

- Hybrid approach for fixation of the wire
 - Fixation by embroidery
 - Inexpensive tool (plates, pins, screws)
 - Easy demolding
 - Easy to clean and reuse

3. Experimental Investigation

Design of test specimen

- Glass fiber preforms
- PU-zone in the center of wire path (actuation zone)
- SMA-wire in meandering pattern
- Variation of design parameters

Design parameters

Wire length	L:	45/70/90 mm
Wire distance	D:	4/6/8 mm
Wire diameter	Ø:	100/200/310 μm

3. Experimental Investigation

Experimental setup

→ **Deformation measurement** (angular) without external force (A)

→ **Force measurement** with blocked deformation (B)

A System for digital image correlation (ARAMIS)

B Load cell

C Thermographic camera

D Specimen

E Power source

4. Results

Activated specimen

4. Results

Wire diameter

- Deformation angle increases for bigger SMA-wire diameters

Wire distance

- Increased blocking force for smaller wire distance
 - Concentrated heat influx effects the austenite transformation of SMA

4. Results

Wire length

- Reduction of blocking force for smaller length
 - Possible loss of pre-strain
- No increase of blocking force for bigger length
 - Flexible bending zone (constant length) of significant influence

5. Conclusion

Integrated MM-FRP actuator structures made by TFP

- All specimens working
 - Bending mainly in the area of the PU-matrix
- Reliable manufacturing method for smart composites with locally defined bending zones
- Suitable for individualized and automated production via TFPprint [4]
- Actuator structures in robotics, valves, clean rooms, etc.

Contact

Sascha Bruk
Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V.
Research Group Complex Structural Components

+49 351 4658 1296
bruk@ipfdd.de